

PRODUCTIVITY PERFORMANCE OF THE INDIAN FOREIGN BANKS: AN EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

*Dr. P. Sanjeevi

Professor

Department of Management Studies, BITS
Visakhapatnam

**Ms. Y. Sunitha

Asst. Professor

Department of Management Studies, BITS
Visakhapatnam

**Mrs. G. Ch.V. Uma Rani

Asst. Professor

Department of Management Studies, BITS
Visakhapatnam

Abstract

Indian banking system has transformed in recent years due to globalization in the world market, which has resulted in fierce competition. In this paper, an attempt has been made to analyze the productivity performance of Foreign Banks in India. Analytical frame of the operational performance per employee in terms of various tools Deposit, Advances, Total business, Total expenses, Establishment, Net profit and Investment, and to different financial segments, purposes; and also the trends over the period under study have been presented. The study is based on secondary data collected from annual reports of five selected foreign banks in India for the study period i.e. 2004-05 to 2015-16. Ratios, t-test, correlation analysis have been used to analyze the present data. The study suggested that foreign banks in India should emphasize on generating more profits per employee by efficient utilization of its capital, total investments, advances, deposits, debt and improving its operational efficiency and productivity performance.

Keywords- Total Business, Deposits per employee Investment per employee, productivity performance

1. Introduction

The financial system of India is complex with a large network of different foreign banks. India has a long history of both public and private banking. Modern banking in India began in the eighteenth century, with the founding of the English Agency House in Calcutta and Bombay. In the first half of the nineteenth century, three presidency banks were founded. After the 1860 introduction of limited liability, private banks began to appear, and foreign banks entered the market. The beginning of the twentieth century saw the introduction of joint stock banks. In 1935 the presidency banks were merged to form the Imperial Bank of India, subsequently renamed the State Bank of India. That same year, India's central bank, the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), began operation. Following independence, the RBI was given broad regulatory authority over commercial banks in India. In 1959 the State Bank of India acquired the state-owned banks of eight former princely states. Thus, by July 1969, approximately 31 percent of scheduled bank branches throughout India were government-controlled as part of the State Bank of India. India's post war development strategy was in many ways a socialist one, and the government felt that banks in private hands did not lend enough to those who needed it most.

The mandate given in the statute drives the corporation to develop entrepreneurship, bring in balanced regional development and drive the industrialization in the state in order to bring the economic development besides creating employment. The quantum of credit deposit ratio and Investment deposit ratios are the major indicators, which throw light on the performance of the foreign banks in fulfilling the responsibilities cast on them.

There are thirty-two (32) foreign banks which are presently operating in India through 308 branches with 1026 ATMs and 72.8% of offsite ATMs. Besides, there are 45 foreign banks operating through representative offices. *Standard Chartered Bank*, the oldest foreign bank that came to India 150 years ago is now operating with 95 branches. It is followed by HSBC, which entered India in 1867, with 50 branches. Citibank has 43 branches and ABN Amro Bank which is known by Royal Bank of Scotland N.V. at present has 31 branches. The other banks that have a double digit branch presence are This research study is an attempt to provide insights with respect to their functioning, productivity per employee and productivity in post-liberalized regime.

2. Literature Review

Pigott (1986)¹ in his study described the policies that have made increasing foreign bank activity possible in nine pacific basin countries, and he provided some aggregate statistics on the size and scope of foreign banking activities.

Nayak (2001)² made an attempt to compare liquidity, productivity and profitability of foreign and domestic banks in India during 1985-86 to 1996-97. The results revealed the productivity in terms of labour, branches and profitability was higher in foreign banks than the domestic banks. Foreign banks are least involved in socio-economic policies of the government, on account of which they registered higher profits.

Abdul Naser (2014)³ found that the financial performance and employee efficiency of foreign banks working in India are better than that of other commercial banks, while public sector banks revealed less profitability but comparatively high stability.

Ibrahim syed (2011)⁴ revealed that scheduled commercial banks in India have significantly improved their financial performance.

chaudhary and sharme (2011)⁵ analysed how efficiently Indian Public sector banks were not as profitable as other scheduled commercial banks.

Pradeep Kumar Keshari (2013)⁶ The theory of globalization suggests that the multinational banks enjoy internationalisation advantage in overcoming imperfection in the international financial market. Affiliates of multinational banks foreign banks in India and elsewhere being part of a worldwide network have access to certain tangible and intangible resources which are not normally available, or only available in a limited amount to domestic banks. The tangible resources include, among other things, foreign funds and highly skilled manpower, while the intangible assets comprise of diversification advantage, management and marketing skills, know-how for introducing new products, better customer services, internationally established marketing network, reputation and goodwill, specialized information on financial market, etc.

¹ Pigott, Charles A., 1986 "Financial reform and the role of foreign banks in pacific basin nations", financial policy and reform in pacific-rim countries.

² Nayak, D.N., 'Liquidity, Productivity and Profitability of Foreign Banks and Domestic Banks in India - A Comparative Analysis', Ibid., pp.305-20.

³ Abdul Naser V (2014), "Financial Performance and Employee Efficiency: A Comparative study of Indian Banks", Indian Journal of Applied Research, Vol. 4, No. 5, pp. 102-104.

⁴ Ibrahim Syed m (2011), "Operational Performance of Indian Scheduled Commercial Banks –an Analysis", International Journal of Business and Management, Vol.6, No.5, pp.120-128.

⁵ chaudhary and sharme (2011) Financial performance Analysis. Business Management, Vol. No.3 pp. 504-508

⁶ Pradeep Kumar Keshari(2013) Operational characteristics, strategies, and performance of foreign and domestic banks in India 22. May 2013 MDI Management Journal, Vol.7, No.2, (July 1994)

3. Research Objectives

Main objectives of the Paper is as follows

- ❖ To study the productivity performance of Foreign Banks in India.
- ❖ To know the productive performance of selected foreign banks in India.
- ❖ To understand the impact of productivity per employee of selected Foreign Banks in India.

4. Research Hypotheses

For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis is to be tested:

Hypothesis H1: Deposits have no positive effect on productivity per employee

Hypothesis H2: Advances have no positive effect on productivity per employee

Hypothesis H3: Business has no positive effect on productivity per employee

Hypothesis H4: Investment has no positive effect on productivity per employee

Hypothesis H5: Total Income has no positive effect on productivity per employee

Hypothesis H6: Total Expenses have no positive effect on productivity per employee

Hypothesis H7: Establishment has no positive effect on productivity per employee

Hypothesis H8: Net Profit has no positive effect on productivity per employee

5. Methodology

The design of the present study is descriptive and analytical in nature and covers the period of 15 years from 2004 to 2016. The data which is required for the analysis and that could fulfill our objectives has been collected mainly from two sources, viz 1) primary and 2) secondary data.

Primary data is collected from the officials and other employees through interviews and discussions with Experts, Chief Finance Officers, Finance Managers, Branch Managers and other Bank officers regarding different aspects of the five foreign banks.

The study is also based on the secondary data obtained from the audited balance sheets and profit & loss accounts, operational reports, budgets, manuals and also the annual reports of ABN AMRO. CITI Bank, Deutsche Bank, Chartered Standard Bank and HSBC . Besides, the facts, figures and findings advanced in similar earlier studies and the RBI Reports, International Financial Reports and government publications are also used to supplement the secondary data.

For assessing the behavior of data statistical techniques have been used such as descriptive, Mean, Standard Deviation, Range, Correlation, t-test, F test are used for this study. For these statistical measures are calculated by using SPSS software.

Financial tools used for ascertain productivity per employee

Deposits per employee = Deposits/Total number of employees

Advances= Advances/Total number of employees

Total Business= Total Business/Total number of employees

Total Income = Total Income/Total number of employees

Investments= Investments/Total number of employees

Total expenses= Total expenses/Total number of employees

Establishment expenses= Establishment expenses/Total number of employees

Net Profit= Net Profit/Total number of employees

6. Analysis of the Study

Productivity analysis of ABN AMRO (Per Employee)

	Deposits per Employee	Advances per Employee	Business per Employee	Investments per Employee	Income per Employee	Expenditure per Employee	Est. Exp. per Employee	Net Profit per Employee
2005-06	4.85	5.55	10.40	2.42	0.95	0.78	0.11	0.16
2006-07	3.68	5.16	8.84	1.75	0.70	0.60	0.09	0.10
2007-08	3.84	4.87	8.71	1.56	0.64	0.56	0.08	0.08
2008-09	4.51	5.18	9.69	1.80	0.86	0.75	0.09	0.11
2009-10	4.89	5.27	10.15	3.04	0.95	0.88	0.14	0.07
2010-11	4.92	5.14	10.06	3.34	1.34	1.33	0.23	0.01
2011-12	6.11	4.94	11.05	2.67	1.06	1.10	0.15	-0.04
2012-13	6.44	4.87	11.32	4.11	1.20	1.12	0.18	0.08
2013-14	6.40	6.15	12.54	3.79	1.28	1.04	0.16	0.24
2014-15	7.86	7.72	15.58	5.62	1.50	1.36	0.21	0.14
2015-16	14.34	13.73	28.07	6.71	2.96	2.52	0.46	0.44
MEAN	5.81	5.87	11.67	3.23	1.16	1.03	0.15	0.12

Source: IBA, Performance Highlights of Foreign Banks in India, Different Issues, Mumbai

Productivity analysis of CITI Bank (Per Employee)

	Deposits per Employee	Advances per Employee	Business per Employee	Investments per Employee	Income per Employee	Expenditure per Employee	Est. Exp. per Employee	Net Profit per Employee
2005-06	10.14	7.56	17.70	3.32	1.57	1.29	0.12	0.28
2006-07	7.80	6.58	14.38	2.95	1.14	0.92	0.09	0.22
2007-08	8.59	7.52	16.11	3.25	1.26	1.05	0.11	0.22
2008-09	7.29	6.33	13.62	3.08	1.10	0.93	0.11	0.17
2009-10	9.65	8.03	17.67	3.86	1.76	1.38	0.15	0.38
2010-11	10.78	8.33	19.10	5.11	2.17	1.72	0.18	0.45
2011-12	11.80	7.95	19.75	6.09	1.66	1.47	0.19	0.19
2012-13	10.64	7.62	18.26	5.71	1.54	1.28	0.19	0.27
2013-14	12.50	9.10	21.60	8.34	1.77	1.40	0.20	0.37
2014-15	12.33	9.64	21.97	8.17	2.02	1.52	0.20	0.50
2015-16	13.85	10.00	23.85	9.07	2.16	1.65	0.19	0.51
MEAN	10.27	7.71	17.98	4.96	1.64	1.35	0.14	0.29

Source: IBA, Performance Highlights of Foreign Banks in India, Different Issues, Mumbai

Productivity analysis of Deutsche Bank (Per Employee)

	Deposits per Employee	Advances per Employee	Business per Employee	Investments per Employee	Income per Employee	Expenditure per Employee	Est. Exp. per Employee	Net Profit per Employee
2005-06	6.06	5.02	11.08	5.45	2.17	1.51	0.15	0.65
2006-07	9.36	6.69	16.05	5.93	2.10	1.90	0.20	0.20
2007-08	4.48	2.64	7.12	3.33	1.19	1.06	0.17	0.13
2008-09	3.10	2.20	5.30	2.76	0.72	0.63	0.17	0.10
2009-10	8.12	5.29	13.40	6.00	1.45	1.23	0.29	0.23
2010-11	8.85	5.50	14.35	5.44	1.81	1.55	0.27	0.27
2011-12	9.81	8.63	18.44	6.04	1.60	1.30	0.34	0.30
2012-13	10.08	9.84	19.92	5.92	1.97	1.53	0.38	0.43
2013-14	12.47	9.29	21.76	6.23	2.33	1.72	0.37	0.61
2014-15	12.55	13.50	26.05	6.40	2.20	1.57	0.31	0.62
2015-16	15.09	16.77	31.87	11.39	2.33	1.91	0.31	0.42
MEAN	7.93	6.73	14.66	5.59	1.72	1.39	0.23	0.33

Source: IBA, Performance Highlights of Foreign Banks in India, Different Issues, Mumbai

Productivity analysis of Standard Chartered Ban (Per Employee)

	Deposits per Employee	Advances per Employee	Business per Employee	Investments per Employee	Income per Employee	Expenditure per Employee	Est. Exp. per Employee	Net Profit per Employee
2005-06	4.47	3.62	8.09	2.26	0.72	0.59	0.05	0.13
2006-07	4.30	3.82	8.12	1.94	0.58	0.46	0.05	0.12
2007-08	4.38	3.71	8.09	1.64	0.63	0.49	0.06	0.14
2008-09	5.13	4.52	9.65	1.79	0.81	0.61	0.09	0.20
2009-10	4.13	3.72	7.85	1.43	0.80	0.61	0.09	0.19
2010-11	5.34	4.79	10.13	1.99	1.12	0.87	0.13	0.24
2011-12	5.96	5.14	11.10	2.29	1.05	0.79	0.13	0.26
2012-13	7.48	6.30	13.77	2.96	1.13	0.87	0.16	0.26
2013-14	8.51	7.39	15.90	3.64	1.45	1.22	0.18	0.23
2014-15	8.62	8.59	17.21	4.26	1.65	1.24	0.18	0.41
2015-16	10.87	10.31	21.18	4.28	1.98	1.74	0.20	0.24
MEAN	5.64	5.11	10.76	2.71	1.04	0.83	0.10	0.21

Source: IBA, Performance Highlights of Foreign Banks in India, Different Issues, Mumbai

Productivity analysis of HSBC (Per Employee)

	Deposits per Employee	Advances per Employee	Business per Employee	Investments per Employee	Income per Employee	Expenditure per Employee	Est. Exp. per Employee	Net Profit per Employee
2005-06	5.20	3.08	8.27	3.32	0.68	0.55	0.07	0.06
2006-07	4.50	3.34	7.83	2.42	0.60	0.52	0.07	0.09
2007-08	5.01	3.37	8.38	2.44	0.63	0.52	0.08	0.10
2008-09	5.15	3.42	8.58	2.09	0.70	0.57	0.09	0.13
2009-10	5.50	3.86	9.36	2.49	0.92	0.76	0.11	0.15
2010-11	6.71	3.71	10.42	4.18	1.21	1.04	0.12	0.17
2011-12	8.34	3.51	11.85	6.18	1.09	0.97	0.12	0.12
2012-13	8.49	4.30	12.79	5.85	1.10	0.86	0.14	0.24
2013-14	11.89	6.87	18.76	7.81	1.64	1.25	0.18	0.38
2014-15	12.03	7.56	19.59	9.56	1.85	1.44	0.23	0.41
2015-16	14.80	8.30	23.10	11.67	1.85	1.55	0.21	0.31
MEAN	0.80	3.98	10.75	4.41	0.96	0.80	0.11	0.16

Source: IBA, Performance Highlights of Foreign Banks in India, Different Issues, Mumbai

7. Statistical Analysis

Correlation Analysis

This part of study has been undertaken to find out the productivity performance of employee to select all five foreign banks. Two set of variables have taken; one dependent variable as size of employee and dependent variable of each selected foreign banks have studied eight independent variables, which are i.e. Deposits, Advances, Business, Investment, Total Income, Total Expenses, Establishment Expenses and Net Profit. Correlation is concern describing the strength of relationship between two variables. It is denoted by 'r' and the simplest formula for computing the appropriate **t value** to test significance of a correlation coefficient employs the t distribution. Degrees of freedom (8-2) = 6 at 5% Level of Significance is 3.143

Correlation results for productivity of an employee of selected five foreign banks

Variable	ABN AMRO		CITI Bank		DB Bank		Standard Chartered Bank		HSBC	
	'r' Value	't' Value	'r' value	't' Value	'r' value	't' Value	'r' value	't' Value	'r' value	't' Value
Deposits	0.85	//3.93// Significant	0.93	//6.19// Significant	0.75	//2.78// Insignificant t	0.81	//3.38// Significant	0.67	//2.21// Insignifica nt
Advances	0.92	//5.82// Significant	0.96	//8.39// Significant	0.65	//2.09// Insignificant t	0.78	//3.05// Insignificant	0.67	//2.21// Insignifica nt
Business	0.90	//5.05// Significant	0.95	//7.45// Significant	0.70	//2.40// Insignificant t	0.80	//3.26// Significant	0.68	//2.27// Insignifica nt
Investment	0.71	//2.46// Insignificant	0.85	//3.95// Significant	0.75	//2.78// Insignificant t	0.68	//2.27// Insignificant	0.49	//1.38// Insignifica nt
Total income	0.83	//3.65// Significant	0.92	//5.82// Significant	0.78	//3.05// Insignificant t	0.77	//2.96// Insignificant	0.73	//2.61// Insignifica nt
Total expenses	0.79	//3.14// Insignificant	0.93	//6.19// Significant	0.79	//3.14// Significant	0.73	//2.61// Insignificant	0.75	//2.78// Insignifica nt
Establishment expenses	0.73	//2.61// Insignificant	0.94	//6.74// Significant	0.89	//4.78// Significant	0.82	//3.51// Significant	0.75	//2.78// Insignifica nt
Net profit	0.12	//0.29// Insignificant	0.40	//1.07// Insignificant	0.61	//1.88// Insignificant t	0.84	//3.79// Significant	0.60	//1.84// Insignifica nt

- Significance at 5% Level Two tailed test ** Table Value (8-2) = 6 is 3.143

Source: Computed

Table: provides pair wise correlation for all the study variables, both dependent and independent with a view to find their degree of linear relationships. An examination of the Pearson Correlation table showed that among all five foreign banks throughout its productivity performance of per employee by taking into consideration eight variables i.e. Deposits, Advances, Business, Investment, Total Income, Total Expenses, Establishment Expenses and Net Profit. All these variables of the five banks have positive correlation. Correlation strength and significance for all eight productivity variables to the five selected banks are: ABN AMRO: All the variables have high positive correlation except Net Profit. Deposits, Advances, Business; variables have seen significant relation and other variables have insignificant relation to determine the productivity per employee.

CITI Bank: All the eight variables have high positive correlation except net profit and also seen all these variables have significant relation with productivity per employee.

Duestche bank: All the eight variables have high positive correlation and observed insignificant relation, except total expenses and establishment expenses; variables have significant relation with productivity per employee.

Standard Chartered Bank: All the eight variables have high positive correlation. It is observed that deposits, business, establishment expenses and net profit have significant relation and other variables has insignificant relation to decide the productivity per employee.

HSBC: All the eight variables have high positive correlation and insignificant relation to choose the productivity per employee. Therefore we concluded that total income, deposits and business are major factors of productivity of employee to all five selected foreign banks.

It can be seen from above table all the financial ratios of scheduled banks have been fluctuate trend from year 2005-06 to 2015-16. Operating ratio, NP ratio and ROE have ranked seventh, Return on Deposit ratio has eight rank and Return on Borrowings has third.

8. Testing Of Hypothesis

In this part test given eight hypotheses are tested by using correlation coefficient to know the relationship strength of productivity of five selected foreign banks to use eight variables and employee size. For this purpose, F- test used for hypothesis result. The hypotheses are as follows:

Summary of “F”- Distribution Inferences productivity of an employee of selected five foreign banks

Variable	ABN AMRO		CITI Bank		DB Bank		Standard Chartered Bank		HSBC	
	'F' value	Significance	'F' value	Significance	'F' value	Significance	'F' value	Significance	'F' value	Significance
Deposits	32.6	.000	89.5	.000	16.54	.001	24.9	.000	10.62	.006
Advances	74.48	.000	157.8	.000	9.39	.009	19.71	.001	10.77	.006
Business	54.55	.000	116.3	.000	12.69	.003	22.43	.000	10.99	.006
Investment	13.45	.003	34.5	.000	16.37	.001	11.38	.005	4.07	.006
Total income	23.56	.000	68.4	.000	20.20	.001	19.89	.001	15.14	.002
Total expenses	22.22	.000	81.21	.000	20.15	.001	15.19	.002	17.14	.001
Establishment Expenses	14.52	.002	100.7	.000	48.79	.000	26.08	.000	16.55	.001
Net profit	0.18	.675	2.5	.137	7.74	.016	13.65	.000	7.40	.017

1. Significance at 5% Level Two tailed test, 2. Table Value (8-1) (5-1) = is 4.12, 3. P-value less than significant level ($\alpha=0.05$)

Source: Computed

Employee: Productivity determinants and its Sub-Hypotheses Results of selected Foreign Banks

Specific Factors	Magnitude and Direction of Hypothesis	Sub-Hypotheses Result				
		ABN	CITI	DB	SCB	HSBC
	Name of the Foreign Bank					
Hypothesis H1	Deposits have no positive effect on productivity per employee	R	R	R	R	R
Hypothesis H2	Advances have no positive effect on productivity per employee	R	R	R	R	R
Hypothesis H3	Business have no positive effect on productivity per employee	R	R	R	R	R
Hypothesis H4	Investment have no positive effect on productivity per employee	R	R	R	R	A
Hypothesis H5	Total Income have no positive effect on productivity per employee	A	A	A	A	A
Hypothesis H6	Total Expenses have no positive effect on productivity per employee	R	R	R	R	R
Hypothesis H7	Establishment have no positive effect on productivity per employee	R	R	R	R	R
Hypothesis H8	Net Profit have no positive effect on productivity per employee	A	A	A	R	A

Source: predictions.

*** A = Hypothesis Accepted**

****R= Hypothesis Rejected**

Inference: This two tables presents the Analysis of variance of productivity determinants of an employee to selected five banks : As per the F-test results, it is clear that the computed values of above mentioned sub-hypotheses are lies above the critical value of 'F' at 5% level of significance. Hypothesis three Consisting of eight sub-hypothesis are represented all eight variables, which are reflected to employee size to decide the productivity performance of five selected banks. It is found that all the variables of F test values greater than critical value at 5% level of significance, where specified sub-hypothesis are rejected except net profit variable is only accepted. Hence, we knew that all the given variables very much influenced the productivity performance of all selected five banks. Net Profit is not effected productivity performance of employee to all the banks except Chartered Standard Bank. Therefore, we concluded that Deposits, Advances, Business, Investments, Total Income, Total Expenses, Establishments Expenses have reflected the productivity performance of employee to the all the selected five banks.

9. Findings

- It is observed that total advances to total deposits have been maintained effectively by ABN AMRO and Standard Chartered Bank.
- As per study analysis, it is marked that Deutsche Bank has ranked first and second rank by ABN bank on Establishment expenses per employee. It is indicated that Deutsche Bank and CITI bank bear higher establishment expenses during the study period
- From the study analysis, it is proved that CITI has ranked first on Investments per employee. It is showed that CITI Bank has highest employee performance with its Investments.
- As per F Test analysis, it is found that all the selected variables of the study very much influenced the productivity performance employee size of all selected five banks.
- It is found that all the variables of F test values greater than critical value at 5% level of significance, where given sub- hypothesis are rejected except net profit variable is only accepted for ABN Bank. Hence, we knew that all the given variables very much influenced the productivity performance of all selected five foreign banks. Net Profit is also influenced productivity performance of branch to all the banks except ABN Bank.

Suggestions

- Deposits per employ except CITI Bank and Deustch Bank, rest of the three foreign banks are better to increase their ample of deposits.
- Investment per employ except CITI Bank, It recommended that rest of the four foreign banks possible to enhance their investment.
- Advances per employee highest and lowest performance had CITI Bank and HSBC Banks. It is suggested that remain four banks including CITI bank must improve their advances.
- Business per employee except CITI Bank rest four banks medium performance as compared to CITI bank. Even, it is suggested that remain four banks better to improve their business for better potential operational performance.
- Income per employee all the selected foreign banks try increase their profits through non-operating income in addition operating income for improved income from employee.
- Both CITI Bank and Deustch Bank have born more operating expenditure as compared to the other three banks with total expenditure of selected banks. It is suggested that CITI bank and Deustch banks should monitor and control their trading aspects under control for minimizing interest expenses per employee,
- Deustch Bank was only bank has been incurred highest establishment expenditure with compared to other four foreign banks. It should be recommended that the Deustch Bank control to minimizing establishment expenses to employee.
- Deustch Bank has highest net income per employee as compared to the other four banks with net profit per employee of selected banks and all foreign banks. It is suggested that rest all four banks try increase their net profit for better net profit per employee.

To conclude, our findings from the productivity performance of five selected foreign in India are moderate during the study period. It is suggested that foreign banks in India should emphasize on generating more profits by efficient utilization of its capital, assets, debt, Investments and Deposits. Profitability of the investments and deployment of liquid assets (cash) should be cared for improved employee productivity efficiency. In addition to that diversification of lending, moderation of transaction costs and management of funds are very much influenced to the foreign banks in India for better productivity performance.

References

- Abdul Naser V (2014), “Financial Performance and Employee Efficiency: A Comparative study of Indian Banks” , Indian Journal of Applied Research, Vol. 4, No. 5, pp. 102-104.
- Ibrahim Syed m (2011), “: Operational Performance of Indian Scheduled Commercial Banks –an Analysis”, International Journal of Business and Management, Vol.6, No.5,pp.120-128.
- Joshi P N (1986), “Profitability and Profit Planning in Banks”, the Journal of Indian Institute of Banks, Vol.57, No.2.
- Koundal Virender (2012),“Performance of Indian Banks in Indian Financial System”, International Journal Social Science and Interdisciplinary Research, Vol.1, No.9, pp.204-213.
- Shrivastav P K (1981), Banking Theory and Practices, Himalaya Publication, Mumbai.
- Sudha Rani D (2013),” Studies on Growth and Performance of Indian Commercial Banks During Global Economic Recession”, International Journal of Computational Engineering and Management, Vol. 16, No.6,pp.39-48.
- Varde V S and Singh S P (1979), “Profitability of Commercial Banks”, Management Accountant, August, pp.778-788.
- RBI Reports
- Finance Management and policy –Bhalla, V.K; Amol publications Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi – 110 002.
- Financial Hand book –Joles I.Bogan.
- Financial Management and policy; J.C Ven Horne; prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
- Khan M.Y. and P.K Jain., Financial Management - Text and Problems, Tata Mc Graw Hill publications, New Delhi.
- Prasanna Chandra, Financial Management- Theory and practice, publications, Tata Mc Graw Hill publications, New Delhi.